

Efficacy of Intraoperative Amniotic Membrane versus Mitomycin-C in Trabeculectomy: A Comparative Randomised Controlled TrialKori S Vijayalaxmi¹, Girimallanavar V Sheetal²¹DNB, Fellowship in Glaucoma, Glaucoma Consultant, MM Joshi Eye Institute, Hubli²MS, DNB, Associate Professor, JGMMMC, KLE University, Hubli

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Trabeculectomy, has been the surgery of choice for the management of glaucoma not controlled with medications. Anti-fibrotic agents, such as Mitomycin C(MMC), has become widely accepted to reduce the amount of fibrosis. Amniotic membrane may be an acceptable replacement to MMC; as it can also provide as a space-occupying component.

Aims And Objectives: To evaluate the Intraocular pressure(IOP) lowering effect of Trabeculectomy with the use of Amniotic membrane transplant(AMT) compared with the standard Trabeculectomy with Mitomycin-C(MMC) in patients with Primary glaucoma.

Materials and Methods: Intraocular pressure lowering effect of Trabeculectomy with the use of Amniotic membrane transplant was compared with the standard Trabeculectomy with Mitomycin-C in patients with Primary glaucoma. It was carried out on the patients attending Glaucoma Department of a tertiary hospital.

Results: Comparison of the two groups with respect to IOP at Post Operative Day(POD) 1 and 1 week, showed no difference, but both groups reached a level of target IOPs. At 1 month follow up, mean IOP control in Group A(underwent Trabeculectomy with Amniotic membrane) was 14.72mmhg with SD +/-3.78 and in Group B(Trabeculectomy with MMC) was 17.60mmhg with SD +/-4.65 with a p value of 0.0203 which was statistically significant. But further follow ups at 3 months and 6 months showed no difference in IOP between Group A and Group B and had reached target IOP levels.

Conclusion: It was observed that both Amniotic membrane and MMC in trabeculectomy proved to be effective adjuvants and results are comparable with minor modifications to the bleb.

Keywords: Trabeculectomy, Amniotic Membrane, Mitomycin C, Glaucoma.

Key Messages: The method of using Amniotic membrane in trabeculectomy is also effective in reducing Intraocular pressure in Glaucoma patients in comparison with earlier methods of using Mitomycin C.

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Introduction

The term "glaucoma" in the present scenario, has been reserved for those people who have established, visually significant optic neuropathy associated with characteristic structural damage to optic nerve and associated visual dysfunction that may be caused by various pathological processes. [1]

It has been estimated that 80 million people worldwide will have glaucoma by the year 2020, of which 11.2 million will be blind. [2] 50% of the affected are not even aware of it. [3]

0.4%-1.6% of people over the age of 40 years have impairment of vision from glaucoma and many more are at risk for developing glaucomatous loss of vision. [4]

The management of glaucoma can be achieved medically, surgically or by a combination of both.

The goal of the management is to keep optic nerve head functioning normally. [5]

Trabeculectomy, first described by Cairns [6] has been the surgery of choice for the management of glaucoma not controlled with medications.

An agent that prevents fibrosis and achieves the same IOP reduction without causing the complications of MMC would be ideal. Success with using anti-VEGF agents has not provided the hoped-for optimistic results. [7]

Amniotic membrane may be an acceptable replacement to MMC; as it can also provide as a space-occupying component. [8]

Bleb grading was done based on in diana Bleb Appearance Grading Scale (IBAGS) [9]

Bleb Height

H0: Flat Bleb

H1: Low Bleb

H2: Medium Bleb

H3: High Bleb

Horizontal Extent

E0: 0 < 1 Clock Hours

E1: 1-2 Clock Hours

E2: >2 - <4 Clock Hours

E3: 4 or > Clock Hours

Vascularity

V0: Avascular white

V1: Avascular Cystic

V2: Mild Vasularity

V3: Moderate Vasularity

V4: Extensive Vasularity

Seidel Test

S0: No Leak

S1: Multiple Pinpoint Leaks

S2: Streaming Leak (within 5 secs)

Aims and Objectives

To evaluate the Intraocular pressure(IOP) lowering effect of Trabeculectomy with the use of Amniotic membrane transplant (AMT) compared with the standard Trabeculectomy with Mitomycin-C (MMC) in patients with Primary glaucoma.

Materials and methods: It was a comparative study to evaluate the Intraocular pressure lowering effect of Trabeculectomy with the use of Amniotic membrane transplant compared with the standard Trabeculectomy with Mitomycin-C in patients with Primary glaucoma.

It was a 1 year hospital based Randomized Prospective Interventional study on 50 eyes of 42 patients with either primary open angle glaucoma or chronic angle closure glaucoma attending Glaucoma department of a tertiary hospital.

Randomization: Single sequence of random assignment was done, eyes in

Group A: underwent Trabeculectomy with Amniotic membrane and,

Group B: Trabeculectomy with MMC.

In the order of their chronological serial number to OT, odd number patients received amniotic membrane and even number patients MMC.

Patients were called for follow up on 1st post-operative day, at the end of 1st week, 1 month, 3 months, 6 months and 1 year.

The main outcome for comparison was IOP-lowering effect of both procedures, functionality, morphology of bleb, bleb survival, additional glaucoma medications to reach target IOP and complications.

Inclusion Criteria:

Primary open angle glaucoma and atleast one of the following:

- Unsatisfactory target intraocular pressure control with topical antiglaucoma treatment
- Optic nerve damage progression on two consecutive visual fields tests
- Increase of cup to disc ratio in a period of 24 months
- Allergy to topical antiglaucoma agents
- Poor compliance.
- Chronic angle closure glaucoma

Exclusion Criteria:

All forms of secondary glaucomas.
One eyed patients
Past or present anterior segment pathology(apart from cataract)
Previously failed glaucoma filtration surgery
Inability or unwillingness to give informed consent.
Inability or unwillingness to return for postoperative follow-up as prescribed in the trial regimen.
Unwillingness to accept randomization.
Pregnancy or female of childbearing age who may be pregnant at the time of treatment. A pregnancy test should be performed on all women of childbearing age to rule out pregnancy
Patients receiving systemic anticoagulant treatment.
Previous conjunctival surgery or scleral pathology

Patients underwent full ocular examination

- BCVA
- Slit lamp evaluation
- IOP by Goldmann applanation tonometer
- Gonioscopy- Zeiss 4 mirror
- Disc and fundus evaluation

- CCT by Ultrasound pachymetry.
- Automated achromatic perimetry using Humphrey field analyser

Results

Age distribution of 50 patients in Group A and Group B

Table 1: Distribution of patients by age groups in Group A and Group B

Age groups	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
<=40yrs	3	12.00	0	0.00	3
41-50yrs	9	36.00	12	48.00	21
51-60yrs	5	20.00	6	24.00	11
>=61yrs	8	32.00	7	28.00	15
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	50

Chi-square= 3.5864 P = 0.3101

Figure 1: Distribution of patients by age groups in Group A

In our study age range was between 34-71yrs with a mean age of 53-74 yrs and SD of +/-10.73.

Most frequent age group among males and females was above 40yrs.

Gender distribution of 50 patients with Primary glaucoma

Table 2: Distribution of male and female patients in Group A and Group B

Sex	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
Male	12	48.00	15	60.00	27
Female	13	52.00	10	40.00	23
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	50

Chi-square= 0.7252 P = 0.3951

Figure 2: Distribution of male and female patients in Group A and Group B

Group A- Out of 25 patients 48% were male and 52% female

Group B - Out of 25 patients 60% were male and 40% female

Gonioscopy in Group A and Group B

Table 3: Distribution of patients by type of gonio finding in Group A and Group B

Gonio	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
Open	14	56.00	16	64.00	30
Closed	11	44.00	9	36.00	20
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	50

Chi-square= 2.0132 P = 0.1569

Figure 3: Distribution of patients by type of gonio in Group A and Group B

Group A- 14(56%) patients had open angles and 11(44%)closed angle.

Group B-16(64%) patients had open angles and 9(36%) closed angle

Preoperative Peripheral Iridotomy in Group A and Group B

Table 4: Distribution of patients by status of pre op PI in Group A and Group B

Pre op PI	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
Present	9	36.00	7	28.00	16
Absent	16	64.00	18	72.00	34
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	50

Chi-square= 0.3638 P = 0.5442

Figure 4: Distribution of patients by status of pre op PI in Group A and Group B

Group A -36% patients underwent PI

Group B-28% patients underwent PI

Central Corneal Thickness(micromilimts)

Table 5: Comparison of Group A and Group B with CCT (in μm) by t test

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value
Group A	25	527.44	41.00	2.4382	0.0185*
Group B	25	504.72	22.14		

*p<0.05

Figure 5: Comparison of Group A and Group B with CCT (in mm)

Group A- Mean CCT -527.44mm

Group B -Mean CCT -504.72mm

CCT corrected IOP

Table 6: Comparison of Group A and Group B with CCT corrected IOPmmhg_preop by t test

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value
Group A	25	32.64	8.62	-0.0667	0.9471
Group B	25	32.80	8.35		

Figure 6: Comparison of Group A and Group B with CCT corrected IOP (mmhg) PI

Group A- CCT Corrected IOP mean was 32.64. SD +/-8.62

Group B- CCT Corrected IOP mean was 32.80.

History of antiglaucoma medications revealed the following data

Table 7: Distribution of patients by AGM in Group A and Group B

AGM	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
β blocker	12	48.00	15	60.00	27
α-agonist	8	32.00	7	28.00	15
PA	16	64.00	15	60.00	31
CAI	15	60.00	10	40.00	25
Miotics	8	32.00	6	24.00	14
Chi-square= 1.4016 P = 0.8448					

Target IOP

Table 8: Distribution of patients by target IOP (mmhg) in Group A and Group B

Target IOP(mmhg)	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
8 to 12	8	32.00	9	36.00	17
13 to 17	10	40.00	9	36.00	19
18 to 22	7	28.00	7	28.00	14
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	50
Chi-square=0.1112 P = 0.9463					

Figure 7: Distribution of patients by target IOP (mmhg) in Group A and Group B

Based on DDLS, History of antiglaucoma medications, duration of disease, history of antiglaucoma medications, previous findings of visual fields, associated comorbid conditions target IOP was set.

Comparison of IOP postoperative between Group A and Group B

Table 9: Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to IOP at POD 1, 1 week, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months by unpaired t test

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value
1 POD	Group A	25	15.68	5.41	-1.1887	0.2404
	Group B	25	17.60	6.00		
1 Week	Group A	25	15.76	4.63	-0.9897	0.3273
	Group B	25	17.04	4.51		
1 Month	Group A	25	14.72	3.78	-2.4013	0.0203*
	Group B	25	17.60	4.65		
3 Months	Group A	25	15.20	3.11	-0.8799	0.3833
	Group B	25	16.00	3.32		
6 months	Group A	25	15.44	3.24	-0.6085	0.5457
	Group B	25	16.00	3.27		

*p<0.05

Figure 8: Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to IOP at POD 1, 1 week, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months

There was no statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B in achieving target IOP at 1 week, 1month, 3months and 6months post operative follow ups.

Table 10: Comparison of POD 1, 1 week, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months with respect to IOP in Group A by paired t test

Time points	Mean	Std.Dv.	Mean Diff.	SD Diff.	Paired t	p-value
1 POD	15.68	5.41				
1 Week	15.76	4.63	-0.08	2.68	-0.1495	0.8824
1 POD	15.68	5.41				
1 Month	14.72	3.78	0.96	4.21	1.1407	0.2652
1 POD	15.68	5.41				
3 Months	15.20	3.11	0.48	4.21	0.5695	0.5743
1 POD	15.68	5.41				
6 months	15.44	3.24	0.24	4.59	0.2612	0.7962
1 Week	15.76	4.63				
1 Month	14.72	3.78	1.04	3.61	1.4400	0.1628
1 Week	15.76	4.63				
3 Months	15.20	3.11	0.56	4.18	0.6692	0.5098
1 Week	15.76	4.63				
6 months	15.44	3.24	0.32	4.03	0.3972	0.6947
1 Month	14.72	3.78				
3 Months	15.20	3.11	-0.48	2.84	-0.8436	0.4072
1 Month	14.72	3.78				
6 months	15.44	3.24	-0.72	3.41	-1.0558	0.3016
3 Months	15.20	3.11				
6 months	15.44	3.24	-0.24	2.47	-0.4856	0.6317

Comparison of IOP between follow up visits in Group A showed 1 POD and 6 months- MD 0.24 SD +/-4.29

1 POD and 1 month – MD 0.96, SD +/-4.21 1 Week and 1 month-MD 1.04 SD +/-3.61

1 POD and 3 months- MD 0.48, SD +/-4.21 1 Week and 3 months –MD 0.56 SD +/-4.81

1 Week and 6 months-MD 0.32 SD +/-4.03

Table 11: Comparison of POD 1, 1 week, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months with respect to IOP in Group B by paired t test

Time points	Mean	Std.Dv.	Mean Diff.	SD Diff.	Paired t	p-value
1 POD	17.60	6.00				
1 Week	17.04	4.51	0.56	3.85	0.7268	0.4744
1 POD	17.60	6.00				
1 Month	17.60	4.65	0.00	3.83	0.0000	1.0000
1 POD	17.60	6.00				
3 Months	16.00	3.32	1.60	5.66	1.4142	0.1701
1 POD	17.60	6.00				
6 months	16.00	3.27	1.60	5.72	1.3997	0.1744
1 Week	17.04	4.51				
1 Month	17.60	4.65	-0.56	3.29	-0.8504	0.4035
1 Week	17.04	4.51				
3 Months	16.00	3.32	1.04	4.36	1.1917	0.2450
1 Week	17.04	4.51				
6 months	16.00	3.27	1.04	3.96	1.3121	0.2019
1 Month	17.60	4.65				
3 Months	16.00	3.32	1.60	4.36	1.8353	0.0789
1 Month	17.60	4.65				
6 months	16.00	3.27	1.60	4.62	1.7321	0.0961
3 Months	16.00	3.32				
6 months	16.00	3.27	0.00	3.37	0.0000	1.0000

*p<0.05

1 POD and 1 month – MD 0 SD +/-0.83

1 Week and 3 months –MD 1.04 SD +/-4.36

1 POD and 3 months- MD 1.60 SD +/-5.66

1 Week and 6 months-MD 1.04 SD +/-3.96

1 POD and 6 months- MD 1.60 SD +/-5.72

5 FU injection post-operatively

1 Week and 1 month-MD 0.56 SD +/-3.29

Table 12: Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to 5FU

5FU	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
1 Dose of 5 FU	1	4.00	1	4.00	2
2 Doses of 5 FU	3	12.00	4	16.00	7
3 Doses of 5 FU	4	16.00	2	8.00	6
None	17	68.00	18	72.00	35
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	50

Figure 9: Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to 5FU

Group A - 8 patients received 5FU injection

Group B – 7 patients received 5FU injection

Other Complications

Table 13: Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to Other Complications

Other Complications	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total	%
Bleb leak and choroidals	0	0.00	1	4.00	1	2.00
Bleb leak on POD1	2	8.00	1	4.00	3	6.00
Bleb leak on POD1 wk	0	0.00	1	4.00	1	2.00
Blebitis	0	0.00	1	4.00	1	2.00
Cystic bleb @1 year	1	4.00	0	0.00	1	2.00

2 eyes in Group A and 2 eyes in Group B had had pin point bleb leak with no evidence of hypotony. It was treated with bandage contact lens and examined at the end of 1 week where seidels test showed no leak.

Bleb Morphology post operative

Table 14: Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to Bleb at 6 months postoperative

Bleb at 6 months postoperative	Group A	%	Group B	%	Total
Good	16	64.00	19	76.00	35
Fair	9	36.00	6	24.00	15
Total	25	100.00	25	100.00	50
Chi-square= 0.8576 P = 0.3551					

Figure 10: Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to Bleb at 6 months postoperative

Group A- 64% good blebs, 36% fair blebs at 6 months post operative

Group B- 76% good blebs, 24% fair blebs, at 6 months post operative

Discussion

Glaucoma is the leading cause of irreversible blindness in the world and constitutes one of the greatest problems in ophthalmologic care worldwide. [10] Intraocular pressure is considered to be the main risk factor for development and progression of glaucoma and indeed the only factor which can be currently modified. The management of glaucoma is directed towards reduction of intraocular pressure to a level that allows good perfusion of optic nerve head so that it remains viable. [11] It can be achieved medically, surgically or combination of both.

Trabeculectomy is one such procedure that reduces intraocular pressure to a level that curtails or significantly slows the process of optic nerve excavation and subsequent field loss.

Age Distribution: Table 1 depicts; 42% of patients were in the age group of 41-50 yrs and 30% were above 60yrs, with a mean age distribution of 53.74 years and SD of +/-10.73. Increasing age therefore becomes a significant risk factor.

Leske MCs, Incidence of open angle glaucoma study found that incidence rate of Primary open angle glaucoma increased from 1.2% at 40-49yrs to 4.2% at age of 70 and more. [12]

In Ocular Hypertension Treatment Study, it was noted that one of the factors that predict the onset of Primary open angle glaucoma is older age, [13]

and as the age increased severity of glaucoma also increased.

Sex Distribution: Among 50 patients, 27 were male and 23 were female, the present study revealed distribution of Primary glaucoma more in male population. In Kahn H A and Miltons; Alternative definition of glaucoma study and effect on prevalence and associations in the Framingham study; authors found out that prevalence of primary open angle glaucoma is higher in men than in women, [14] which was comparable to the present study.

Gonioscopy: In this study, Table 3; Group A: Out of 25 patients 14(56%) of them had open angles, 11(44%) had angle closure. Group B: Out of 25 patients 16(64%) of them had open angles, 9(36%) had angle closure. There was no statistically significant difference between the two.

Preoperative PI: Table 4 depicts that preoperative PI was done in 9(36%) patients in Group A and in 7(28%) patients in Group B

Central Corneal Thickness: All patients were evaluated for Central corneal thickness using Corneal pachymetry (TomeyPachy Meter SP-3000) to rule out falsely high or low IOP.

Table 5, showed mean CCT – 527.44 microns in Group-A, 504.72 microns in Group B.

CCT corrected IOP: In this study preoperative IOP was predominantly in the range of 22mmhg-52mmhg with a mean of 32.64+/-8.62 mmhg in Group A and 32.80+/-8.35 mmhg in Group B. Postoperatively IOP in Group A reached set target level and was with a mean of 15.44+/-3.24 at 6 months follow up and in Group B also reached the

set target level IOP and was with a mean of 16.00 \pm 3.27 at 6 months. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups in terms of target IOP.

History of Antiglaucoma Medications (AGM):

Table:7 shows the distribution of patients by AGM in group A and group B. Majority of people in this study used Prostaglandin analogues, 64% in Group A and 60% in Group B. 48% patients in Group A and 60% patients in Group B used Beta blockers. 8% of patients in Group A and 7% in Group B used Alpha-agonists. And it was also seen that patients were on more than one (multiple drugs) drug for IOP control.

Duration of AGM in Group A was with a mean of 7.04 months and in Group B was with a mean 8.53 months. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups, related to exposure to antiglaucoma medications.

Collaborative Initial Glaucoma Treatment Study (CIGTS):

was initiated to evaluate whether local medical therapy or trabeculectomy is the better initial treatment for patients with newly diagnosed open-angle glaucoma. The results of the questionnaire showed only minor differences between the two groups. The medically treated patients reported slightly more ocular symptoms than the patients in the trabeculectomy group. [15-17]

Target IOP: Based on disc findings and associated visual field changes, duration of disease, number of anti-glaucoma medications and associated comorbidities target IOP was set for each eye.

Table 8: depicts that 32% patients in Group A and 36% patients in Group B were in the target IOP range of 8-12, 40% patients in Group A and 36% patients in Group B were in the target IOP range of 13-17, 28% patients in Group A and Group B were in the target IOP range of 18-22mmhg.

Post-Operative Follow Up: Patients were followed up on POD 1, 1 week, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months Post operative day 1- Five eyes in Group-A and 4 eyes in Group-B had moderate AC reaction, for which aggressive steroids were given and followed up. Post operatively two eyes in Group- A and two eyes in Group B had pin point bleb leak with no evidence of hypotony. It was treated with bandage contact lens and examined at the end of 1 week where siedels test showed no leak. All eyes in both groups had AC depth of Van-Herrick's grading 3-4.

Nine eyes of Group A had low height bleb of H1 with IOP > target IOP with AC depth of Van-Herrick's grading 3-4, underwent gentle bleb massage and bleb was formed resulting in height of H2-H3 and drop in the IOP and patients were advised bleb massage thrice a day. Similarly eleven

eyes in Group B had low bleb height and improved with bleb massaging.

Post- operative 1 week follow up showed, decrease in inflammation in the above mentioned eyes and 9 eyes in Group-A and 11 eyes in Group-B where bleb massage was advised, had reached bleb height H2-H3 and extent of bleb was E2 with IOP less than target levels.

While bleb revision with adjunctive MMC is an effective treatment in cases of bleb failure, glaucoma surgeons have been recently examining the effectiveness of amniotic membrane transplantation. The amniotic membrane is made of strong and stable collagen, and has good anti-inflammatory, antifibrotic, and antiangiogenic properties. In glaucoma filtration surgery, the healing response is characterized by fibroblast outgrowth, and the fibrosis has been reported to be delayed more by an amniotic membrane than with conventional conjunctival closure [18]

Fujishima et al, transplanted the amniotic membrane under a scleral flap and sutured it to the sclera. For the 14 eyes of the 13 patients with treatment-resistant glaucoma, the IOP was reduced to 20 mmHg after surgery in 13 eyes. [19]

Drolsum et al used a large amniotic membrane, and sutured it to the scleral surface, and one end was positioned under the scleral flap and the other end was secured to subconjunctival tissue. The mean preoperative IOP was 32.2 mmHg, and the mean postoperative IOP was 16.4 mmHg. Although there were differences in the methods and definition of success, they reported that amniotic membrane transplantation was good for the revision of failed glaucoma filtering blebs. [20]

These reports encouraged the use of amnion group, six cases (50%) were fornix-based, and all of the cases in the non-amnion group were limbus based because a fornix-based conjunctival flap allowed to fix the amniotic membrane at the edge easier than a limbus-based flap.

Comparison of Group A and Group B with respect to IOP at POD 1 and 1 week, showed no difference, but both groups reached a level of target IOPs. At 1 month follow up, mean IOP control in Group A was 14.72mmhg with SD \pm 3.78 and in Group B was 17.60mmhg with SD \pm 4.65 with a p value of 0.0203 which was statistically significant. But further follow ups at 3 months and 6 months showed no difference in IOP between Group A and Group B and had reached target IOP levels.

As shown in Table:9 At one year follow up, the two groups were similar in terms of IOP and need for ocular hypotensive medications without compromising long-term control of IOP.

As shown in Table 10: Comparison of IOP between follow up visits in Group A showed significant difference between 1POD and 1 Month with a mean difference of 0.96 which can be attributed as a result of immediate post-operative inflammation and early bleb vascularisation which was alleviated by next follow-up.

As shown in Table 11: In Group B: Comparison of IOP between follow up visits in Group B showed no significant difference between 1 POD and 1 month, but showed a significant result at 3 and 6 months follow up with a mean of 1.60. The above variation can also be attributed to immediate post operative inflammation and bleb vascularisation.

Budenz et al stated that amniotic membrane transplantation did not offer an effective alternative to conjunctival advancement for repair of a leaking filtering bleb. The postoperative IOP in their amniotic membrane transplantation group was relatively higher than in the conjunctival advancement group, although the difference was not statistically significant. [21]

Demir et al concluded that amniotic membrane transplantation can depress wound healing in a rabbit model of glaucoma. However, the amniotic membrane was less effective than MMC. [22]

Li et al, [23] described the usefulness of amniotic membrane transplantation for the repair of conjunctival button holes during trabeculectomy with MMC.

They also discussed better ways to use amniotic membrane during glaucoma surgery. They concluded that amniotic membrane transplantation was

useful when used as a platform for re-epithelialization as opposed to tissue replacement for conjunctiva after bleb excision. They reported on the importance of the way the amniotic membrane was handled to obtain good surgical results.

Recently, Sheha et al[24], reported that amniotic transplantation in trabeculectomy with MMC for refractory glaucoma had achieved better IOP reduction than trabeculectomy with MMC alone. Although we sutured the amniotic membrane over the scleral flap, they placed a single layer of amniotic membrane under and around the scleral flap. All of these findings indicate that improvements in the surgical procedures for handling and placing the amniotic membrane are needed.²⁵

Early Post Operative Complication

The most frequent complication was early bleb vascularisation (Figure 11) which was noticed in 8 patients in Group A and 7 patients in Group B which was considered to be one of the major causes of bleb failure.

To prevent bleb failure, 0.1cc of 50mg/ml 5-Fluorourasil injection was given sub-conjunctivally 3 clock hours away from the site of the bleb. Table 12 shows that 4% of eyes required 1 dose of 5-FU, 12% eyes required 2 doses of 5-FU 4 weeks apart, 16% of eyes required 3 doses of 5-FU 4 weeks apart in group A and 4% of eyes required 1 dose of 5FU, 16% eyes required 2 doses of 5FU with 4 weeks apart and 8% of eyes required 3 doses of 5 FU 4 weeks apart in group B for the bleb to become avascular with bleb grading of H2E2V0-1 and there was change in the mean IOP after 5-FU injection which was statistically significant.

Figure 11: Vascularised Bleb

A Mohammad A Rashad [26] evaluated the success rate of a modified bleb needling technique with 5FU in eyes with previous glaucoma surgery that had elevated intraocular pressure. The overall success rate was 92%. Repeated needling with adjunctive 5-FU proved a highly effective, safe alternative

to revive filtration surgery rather than another medication or surgery.

A Suzuki R, Susanna-Jr R [19] compared the efficacy of transconjunctival needling revision with 5-fluorouracil versus medical treatment in glaucomatous eyes with uncontrolled intraocular pressure

due to encapsulated bleb after trabeculectomy. Results showed mean intraocular pressure at the final 12-month follow-up was lower in the transconjunctival needling revision group compared to the medical treatment group.

A Ewing and Stamper [20] were the first to describe the use of 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) in bleb needle revisions. They performed subconjunctival injections of 5-FU during the postoperative period and reported a 91.6% success rate with 63.6% (11 of 12 patients) requiring adjunctive medications.

Figure 12: Avascular Bleb

Other complications were- one patient in Group B had choroidals which was treated with oral and topical steroids and recovered. At one year follow up one patient in Group A had Cystic bleb.

The serious complications of trabeculectomy are not very frequent but complications of clinical significance do occur.

Visual field examination done through Humphreys visual field analyser revealed no significant change in perimetry report between 1st and 6th month of follow up in all eyes, hence both the procedure successfully maintained IOP in target IOP range with modifications to the bleb and best corrected visual acuity was corresponding with amount of glaucomatous damage.

8 eyes in Group A and 7 eyes in Group B showed bleb vascularisation with resultant increase in IOP, bleb scores of which were suggestive of impending bleb failure, hence for survival of the bleb intervention was done by giving sub-conjunctival 5-FU injection and noticed avascularity along with significant drop in IOP post 5-FU injection. This highlights the importance of the early post operative follow-up visits after trabeculectomy and the chance to save some of the filtering blebs.

It would rather be a more rational and interesting study if intervention would have not been done for vascularisation and to see the final outcome of trabeculectomy procedure. There was lacunae in the study because of short duration of follow ups and recommend long follow up studies on the same.

Finally aim of our study to evaluate the IOP lowering effect of trabeculectomy with the use of Amniotic membrane was same as standard trabeculectomy with MMC .

Conclusion

It was observed that both Amniotic membrane and MMC in trabeculectomy proved to be effective adjuvants and results are comparable with minor modifications to the bleb.

Declaration of patient consent: The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate patient consent forms. In the form the patient(s) has/have given his/her/their consent for his/her/their images and other clinical information to be included in the journal. The patients understand that their names and initials will not be published and due efforts will be made to conceal their identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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